

PENSION PROVISION OF MILITARY PERSONNEL: DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF LEGISLATION

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Article 39 of the Constitution of Uzbekistan states that “Everyone has the right to social security in old age, disability, as well as in the event of loss of a breadwinner and in other cases provided for by law” [1]. One of the main types of social security is pensions. According to the data, today about 11% of the total population of Uzbekistan (3.9 million people) receive pensions and benefits, and their number is growing by 200-250 thousand people annually. Among them are servicemen leaving the Armed Forces.

In order to realize the rights of servicemen to pensions, on April 28, 1990, the Law "On pensions for servicemen" was adopted. Pensions of military personnel of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan are regulated by this Law [2].

An analysis of pension provision in the CIS countries shows that independent national laws have been developed in this regard.

In particular, on February 12, 1993, the Law of the Russian Federation "On pensions for military personnel, law enforcement officers, persons serving in penitentiary bodies and institutions, and members of their families" was adopted. According to Kobzev, although he left the post-Soviet space, pension relations in this country are being rebuilt.

The law of the Russian Federation requires 20 years of military service in order to receive a seniority pension. At the same time, military personnel will receive a pension in the amount of at least 50% of the money supply.

Ukraine has also adopted a separate law on this issue. In particular, the Law of April 9, 1992 “On Pensions for Demobilized and Other Citizens” establishes a length of service of 20 years and provides that 50% of the pension is calculated on the basis of pensions[4].

In Tajikistan, a separate law on military pensions was adopted in 1994 [5]. According to him, the total length of military service required for retirement was 25 years. However, 65% of the money supply is defined as the base amount for calculating the pension.

In the Kyrgyz Republic, on May 7, 1993, a national law “On military pensions” was adopted. It sets the general length of service for granting a pension at 20 years and requires that a cash allowance of 55% of the basic pension be taken into account.

Now, if you pay attention to the legislation of Uzbekistan, it takes at least 20 years of seniority to receive a seniority pension. At the same time, the pension is established by the military: for 20 years of service - in the amount of 40% of the allowance, as well as upon dismissal by age or illness - in the amount of 45% of the allowance. From the above comparative analysis it can be seen that Uzbekistan has the lowest basic pension for military personnel in the former Soviet Union. According to article 20 of the Old Law, our military personnel are entitled to a disability pension if they became disabled during the service or within 3 months after dismissal from service, or if they became disabled as a result of concussion, injury, injury or illness. The Russian scientist N. Tyutyunov noted that while a disability pension is not assigned to all military personnel, it is considered more affordable and convenient than the size of the pension assigned for long service. In fact, we have 75% of the money supply for the invalids of the war of the 1st group, the 2nd group, 50% for the 3rd group; For other reasons, disabled people of groups 1 and 2 are set at 55% for military personnel and 3 groups for disabled people 30%. However, after the appointment of a pension, a soldier receiving a pension must undergo a TMEC inspection once a year (otherwise, the payment of the pension will be suspended). With a change in disability group, the size of the pension will also change. For example, conscripts with disabilities of 3 groups cannot receive a pension. Or, if during the examination of TMEC it is established that a person with a disability is healthy, his / her pension will be suspended. Moreover, if the year of military service is less than 20 years, then a soldier dismissed from the reserve, even if he served 19 years under a contract, is deprived of the right to receive a military pension and a total retirement age (60 years for men and 55 years for women) waiting.

One of our jurists M. Ziyadullaev considers it necessary to resolve the issue of paying a pension to a disabled person of the 3rd group [7]. True, in a certain sense this idea is appropriate. This is due to the fact that conscripts can be disabled in the service. However, in the current order, they relate to off-budget pension provision departments and are not paid to the 3rd group. Firstly, they do not form the structure of cash benefits for calculating pensions, and the budget does not allocate funds for these issues.

Under section 32 of the Military Pensions Act, if a soldier dies in the line of duty, his family is entitled to a survivor's pension. A pension is also assigned to the family of a serviceman in the event of his death within 3 months after the

dismissal or in the event of death as a result of a concussion, wound, injury or disease acquired upon dismissal.

Family members of a pensioner are disabled dependents of a serviceman. They must apply within 6 months. In this case, untimely receipt of a pension is paid in branches of the People's Bank for an indefinite period.

In our opinion, in order to improve the state pension for military personnel in Uzbekistan, it is first of all necessary to adopt a new version of the National Independent Law "On pensions for military personnel and members of their families". With this law, it will be possible to calculate the number of applications, internships and salaries in the foreign pension system, introduce the practice of electronic receipt of pension information in the national military pension system, and digitize pensions. This will serve to ensure and improve the pension rights of military personnel.

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